

Physiological Quality Assessment on Accelerated Ageing of Eight Pigeon Pea Genotypes Harvested at Low Moisture Contents

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Abstract: Seed ageing is the main challenge of seed storage while the maintenance of viability in storage is germane in seed quality preservation. Physiological quality assessment on accelerated ageing of eight pigeon pea genotypes harvested at low moisture contents was evaluated. The study was conducted in the Laboratory of the Department of Crop Science, University of Agriculture and Environmental Sciences, Umuagwo, Nigeria. The seeds of the eight pigeon pea used (A8125, AO78-99, AO/TB-78-9, CITA-1, CITA-2, CITA-3, 1CPL 87 and NSWCC-18) were collected from the International Institution of Tropical Agriculture, Ibadan. The seeds were dried and stored in the incubator at 45°C and 85% Relative humidity (RH) conditioned using NaCl and germination was determined at 100 - day time course during storage on 50 seeds. The experiment was laid out in a completely randomized randomized design with three replications. Data were collected on seed germination, seedling length and seedling vigour index and subjected to Analysis of Variance (ANOVA). Treatment means were separated using New Duncan Multiple Range Test at 5% probability level. PROBIT modeling was also used to estimate potential longevity. Significant differences occurred in the seed quality of the pigeon pea seeds due to differences in genotypes and ageing duration. Genotype CITA-1 displayed superiority over all the other genotypes with estimated storage of (6.31 months) thus, recommended for future seed improvement programme.

Keywords: Deterioration, storage life, probit modelling, seed quality.

Introduction

Pulses are important nutritional legumes for billions of people around the world, although their functional attributes and benefits have not yet been fully explored among which are beans, peas, chickpeas and lentils (Singh, 2017). Global demand for these species has increased tremendously, including pigeon pea (*Cajanus cajan*). Pigeon pea is one of the most valuable legumes in the world. It is referred to as 'orphan crop' because it falls into the category of least researched crops worldwide (Prochnow *et al.*, 2015). It is a very important source of protein in many parts of Nigeria and elsewhere. The chemical composition of this crop revealed that, it is rich in protein (21.5%), while the fiber content is about 2.5% (Amandeep *et al.*, 2017). Pigeon pea is an important crop for green manure, providing up to 90 kg nitrogen per hectare (Manikandam and Sivasubramaniam., 2015). The crop contributes to sustainable agriculture and also helps to enrich the soil by its ability to fix nitrogen from the atmosphere. However, despite its enormous benefits, post-harvest pests' infestation has been a menace that affects the production of the crop in Nigeria and across the world, causing significant yield losses, especially in developing

countries like Nigeria. In order to substantiate the resilience of African populations to food insecurity, there is need to embrace crops diversification in order to reduce post-harvest losses. According to (Abdollahpour *et al.*, 2020) pigeon pea harvesting operations usually commence when the grain moisture content is about 12–15%. According to previous report with good management strategies, the longevity and agricultural productivity of cereals can be enhanced (Yang *et al.*, 2021). Further studies reported that grain moisture content is a key indicator of the appropriate harvest period of seeds on the field and could also be used to effectively stabilize and maximize cereal production, thereby increasing farmers' income (Khan *et al.*, 2017). One of the ways to ensure increased yields of cereals, seeds must be harvested at physiological maturity, or better still, at field maturity. High moisture content decreases the quality of pigeon peas and cereals generally.

Seed ageing is a natural phenomenon that normally affects seed emergence and seedling growth among other things, hence, the need to carry out seed vigour tests to be able to evaluate performance of the seed lots under various strenuous environmental conditions. Accelerated seed ageing

technique is a widely used tool for estimating and evaluating seed quality. This help to give better indications of probable field emergence than germination and growth tests (Kehinde *et al.*, 2018). According to (Sudha *et al.*, 2020), Improvements in seedling quality could only occur when both morphological and physiological attributes are considered. Kuai *et al.*, (2016) highlighted some criteria used by farmers in their choice of seeds, which are; high yielding crop variety, ability of crop variety to tolerate or resist pest and disease attack, ability of crop variety to mature on time and the ability of crop variety to store well. According to (Hussein *et al.*, 2012), it is important for seed specialists and consumers to understand that vigour tests are not formulated to predict the exact number of seedlings that will emerge or survive in the field, but rather to know the strength and threshold of seeds (Elli *et al.*, 2019). However, through these techniques, the storability potential of seed lot under varying environmental conditions can be predicted. Scanty information is available as regards to the use of these techniques for pigeon pea production in Nigeria. This research would be important as it will provide information on accelerated ageing test, on the vigour and storability potential

of pigeon pea genotypes. The purposes of vigour tests is to indicate whether causality may be expected from a high germinating seed lot, if placed under adverse environmental conditions either on the field, during transportation or even storage (Benaseer *et al.*, 2018). The findings from this study will go a long way in determining and recommending a more viable and high quality seeds of pigeon pea to farmers thus improving the yields of pigeon pea. Based on these facts, the physiological quality assessment on accelerated aging of eight pigeon pea genotypes harvested at low moisture contents was evaluated.

Materials and Methods

Seed source

The eight pigeon pea genotypes used for the experiment were collected from the International Institute of Tropical Agriculture (IITA) Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria. The eight pigeon pea genotypes were A8125, AO78-99, AO/TB-78-9, CITA-1, CITA-2, CITA-3, 1CPL 87 and NSWCC-18. The pigeon pea seeds were multiplied in the Teaching and Research Farm of Crop Science Department, of University of Agriculture and Environmental Sciences (UAES), Umuagwo, Imo State from April to December, 2022 at lat(5° 18' 12.60"N long. 6°56' 26.39"E). The seed were harvested at 12% moisture content. Seeds of eight genotypes of pigeon pea seeds were subjected to accelerated

ageing tests(AA) in an oven set at 45°C for 100 days (January- April, 2023) in the Crop Science Departmental Laboratory of UAES University of Agriculture and Environmental Sciences, Imo State, Nigeria. The seeds were packed into net bags and placed in desiccators adjusted to 85% RH by a saturated solution of NaCl in distilled water and kept in an incubator set at 45°C. Physiological evaluations were done at regular intervals during the storage to maintain 85% RH using a digital thermometer (DMT-489). The thermometer was positioned placed in the seed compartment of the desiccators.

Data Collection

Triplicate samples of fifty seeds were taken for viability and vigour test at 0, 3, 5, 10, 20, 35, 50, 70, and 100 days after accelerated aging as follow:

Seed Germination: Fifty seeds in three replications for each genotype were placed inside paper towel. Each paper towel was soaked with 10ml of distilled water. The paper towels were placed into germination chamber at 25°C and germination count was taken for 8 days. Evaluations on germination were taken at 3rd, 5th, 7th and 8th days.

1. Seed germination was then determined as:

$$\frac{\text{Germination count after 8 days}}{\text{Number of seeds sown}} \times 100$$

Number of seeds sown

2. Seedling Length (cm): This was determined by taking 5 seedling samples from each paper towel by measuring the length in centimeters (cm) from tip of the cotyledon to the point of radicle emergence.

3. Seedling Vigour Index:

This was determined according to procedure reported by Kehinde (2018), as follows:

$$\frac{\text{Standard germination} \times \text{Seedling length}}{100}$$

100

Data Analysis

The seed germination, seed viability and vigour index data from the accelerated aging tests of seed lots, were subjected to PROBIT analysis according to the procedure of Ellis and Roberts (1980). The data on seed viability and vigour were further subjected to treatment means using Duncan's Multiple Range Test at 5% probability level.

Results and Discussion

Results

Table 1 shows the mean square values of seed quality of eight pigeon pea genotypes after accelerated ageing. The result revealed that ageing duration; genotype effect and their interaction were highly significant ($P \leq 0.01$) on all the seed quality evaluated.

The interactive effect of ageing duration and genotype on seed viability of pigeon pea is presented in Table 2. Genotypes CITA-1 recorded statistically highest germination values of 87.04% followed by AO78-99 (83.09%) while NSWCC-18 (52.01%) had the lowest value (52%). At 3 days of ageing, the highest

germination value was recorded in genotypes CITA-1(74%) while AO/TB-78-9 and NSWCC-18 jointed had the least values of (44%). For the rest of ageing duration, CITA-1 consistently maintained the lead while AO/TB-78-9, CITA-3 and ICPL-87 recorded the lowest values of (0%) after 100 days of storage.

Table 1 Mean square values for seed quality traits of eight pigeon pea genotypes after accelerated ageing.

Source of Variation	DF	GP%	SL (cm)	Svi
Ageing Duration (A)	8	6968.92**	349.72	213.32
Genotype (G)	8	1547.02**	31.34**	26.16**
A x G	82	28.39**	0.28**	27.27**
Error	203		2.16	2.07

** Significant at 1% probability level, * Significant at 5% probability level GP: Germination Percentage, SL: Seedling Length and SVI: Seedling Vigour Index,

Table 2 Interactive effect of ageing duration and genotype on seed germination of eight pigeon pea genotypes

GENOTYPES	Ageing Duration (Days)								
	0	3	5	10	20	35	50	75	100
A8125	69.02b	54.0bc	70.04a	59.05cd	59.01cd	59.34cd	39.01cd	43.02a	30.21a
AO78-99	83.09a	59.0b	65.05ab	54.06cd	54.00cd	39.98cd	44.03cd	23.22cd	5.04de
AO/TB-78-9	52.08c	44.0cd	55.06cd	39.04cd	35.00cd	29.22cd	34.08cd	14.62e	0.00e
CITA-1	87.04a	74.0a	70.03a	61.04cd	44.09cd	44.12cd	39.55cd	39.44a	19.00cd
CITA-2	72.05ab	54.0bc	50.02cd	59.0cd	44.04cd	49.61cd	49.56cd	29.22cd	14.00cd
CITA-3	59.01c	54.0bc	50.03cd	49.07cd	43.03cd	24.99cd	24.44cd	19.24e	0.00e
ICPL 87	79.02b	73.0a	50.04cd	54.08cd	41.01cd	29.55cd	34.07cd	29.34cd	0.00e
NSWCC-18	52.01c	44.0d	40.09cd	34.06cd	44.02cd	46.33cd	37.09cd	29.45cd	28.20a

Means followed by the same alphabet are not different from another at 5% probability level according to Duncan's Multiple Range Test.

Table 3: shows Interactive effect of ageing duration and genotype on seedling vigour index of eight pigeon pea genotypes. Genotypes AO78-99 recorded statistically highest SVI values of (13.55) while CITA-3 had the least SIV value of (6.34) at 0days. However, at 3 days of ageing process, ICPL-87, A8125 and AO78-99 with SIV values of 8.08, 8.45 and 8.39, respectively recorded the highest while NSWCC-18 (5.01) had the least SIV value. For the rest of ageing duration except at 100days, CITA-1 consistently maintained the lead while all genotypes recorded the lowest values of (0%) except A8125 (1.22) and NSWCC-18 (1.44) after 100 days of storage.

Interactive effect of ageing duration and genotype on seedling length of eight pigeon pea genotypes was presented in Table 4. At 0 days of storage, A8125 and AO78-99 jointly led the seedling length value of 17.34 and 15.45cm, respectively. Similarly, at 3 days of ageing period, genotype A8125 with (16.33cm) had the highest value while the rest genotypes values were not statistically different from one another. Also, the seedling length value diminishes as the number of days in storage increases. At 100days of storage, CITA-3, ICPL-87 and AO/TB-78-9 had the least values of seedling length while CITA-1 and A8125 with values 3.95 and 3.45cm jointly had least values.

Table 3 Interactive effect of ageing duration and genotype on seedling vigour index of eight pigeon pea genotypes

Genotypes	Ageing Duration (Days)								
	0	3	5	10	20	35	50	75	100
A8125	12.02a	8.45a	7.05a	6.03cd	5.08cd	4.09cd	2.77cd	2.43ab	1.22cd
AO78-99	13.55a	8.39a	9.08ab	6.06cd	5.03cd	2.34cd	2.44cd	0.04cd	0.00cd
AO/TB-78-9	7.34ab	5.89d	6.09bcd	4.09cd	3.02cd	2.34cd	2.23cd	0.00cd	0.00cd
CITA-1	11.98a	9.08a	10.02a	6.06cd	4.06cd	4.89cd	3.65cd	2.34ab	0.12cd
CITA-2	9.06a	6.02bc	4.02cd	5.03cd	3.09cd	3.45cd	2.89cd	1.22ab	0.32cd
CITA-3	6.34ab	6.07bc	4.09cd	4.01cd	3.08cd	1.33e	1.22cd	0.89cd	0.44cd
ICPL 87	9.55a	8.06a	5.06cd	4.04cd	2.02cd	2.22e	2.45cd	1.22ab	0.00cd
NSWCC-18	7.98ab	5.01d	5.01cd	3.08cd	4.09cd	4.78cd	2.69cd	1.33ab	1.44cd

Means followed by the same alphabet are not different from another at 5% probability level according to Duncan's Multiple Range Test.

Table 4 Interactive effect of ageing duration and genotype on seedling length of eight pigeon pea genotypes

Genotypes	Ageing Duration (Days)								
	0	3	5	10	20	35	50	75	100
A8125	17.34a	16.33a	11.21cd	10.67cd	9.00cd	8.01cd	7.22a	5.88cd	3.45a
AO78-99	15.45a	12.78ab	13.87ab	12.76cd	9.00cd	6.56cd	5.87a	2.34cd	1.04ac
AO/TB-78-9	13.66ab	13.09ab	12.89cd	10.45cd	9.01cd	8.56cd	6.67a	5.22cd	0.04ac
CITA-1	13.44ab	13.45ab	12.50cd	11.89cd	9.03cd	9.98cd	7.65a	6.11cd	3.95a
CITA-2	12.76ab	11.34ab	10.90e	9.23cd	8.06cd	7.22cd	5.33a	3.02cd	2.33ab
CITA-3	12.99ab	11.22ab	10.22e	9.98cd	8.09cd	7.08cd	6.33a	4.33cd	0.00ac
1CPL 87	11.01ab	11.12ab	10.10e	8.03cd	7.09cd	6.99cd	5.01a	4.22cd	0.00ac
NSWCC-18	13.71ab	13.11ab	13.88ab	11.0cd	10.01cd	9.20cd	7.02a	6.03cd	4.77a

Means followed by the same alphabet are not different from another at 5% probability level according to Duncan's Multiple Range Test.

Table 5 showed the estimate of probit seed longevity parameter for eight pigeon pea genotypes after accelerated ageing for 100days. All the genotypes recorded low rate of deterioration (slope) ranging from -0.04 to -0.01. CITA-1 had the highest time taken

(115.20 days) to lose 1 probit viability followed by CITA-3(84.74days) while A8125 (20.26days) had the lowest. The highest estimate of seed storage life was recorded in CITA-1 (6.31months) followed by AO/TB-78-9 (4.04 months) while genotypes AO78-99 had the lowest (0.81).

Table 5 Estimate of probit seed longevity parameter for eight pigeon pea genotypes after accelerated ageing for 100days

Genotype	Intercept	slope	Sigma	Seed half life	*storage life (months)
CITA-1	0.37	-0.01	115.20	102.30	6.31
AO/TB-78-9	0.55	-0.02	36.45	66.12	4.01
AO78-99	0.80	-0.02	62.95	10.16	0.81
CITA-2	0.62	-0.02	63.44	79.38	4.56
CITA-3	0.32	-0.02	84.74	51.84	2.86
1CPL 87	0.17	-0.03	52.51	21.30	1.35
NSWCC-18	0.42	-0.03	50.20	42.14	2.01
A8125	0.10	-0.04	20.26	52.38	2.75

Ki- Intercept, $1/\sigma$ - slope, σ -Time taken for seed lot to lose 1 probit viability.

P_{50} -Seed half or measure of time to 50% seed viability in storage

**Storage life was estimated as half life (P_{50}) values multiply by 2 then divide by 30days of a month

Discussion

This study has further showed that artificial ageing methods have tendencies of causing physiological damage of seeds as evidenced by sporadic decrease in seed germination %, seed viability and germination rate over time. Seeds are living entities and are therefore, prone to ageing during storage; however the rate of deterioration varies from species to species and are dependent on many factors like moisture content, temperature, and relative humidity amongst others. The Overall results revealed that accelerated ageing can be used to predict the storability of pigeon pea seeds. In this study, accelerated ageing had significant effect on the physiological quality of the eight pigeon pea genotypes evaluated. The significant differences observed among the genotypes were mostly due to genetic make-up of the genotypes, which implies that there is an opportunity for selection of genotypes with superior seed quality and longevity performance.

This is in consonant with the findings by Hussein *et al.*, 2012 and Kehinde *et al.*, (2019), who also reported significant variance in seed quality and longevity performance of maize and watermelon seeds respectively. This study has further

established that considerable variation occurred among the genotypes and ageing duration on seed viability, seedling vigour and potential longevity of pigeon pea seed. This study revealed highly significant interaction between the genotypes and ageing duration had effect on the seed quality of the eight pigeon genotypes. This implies that ageing duration was significantly affected by the seed quality among the eight genotypes evaluated. To corroborate the findings above, substantial variation was observed by Elli *et al* (2019) in pigeon pea and Adebisi *et al.* (2020) in groundnut and after accelerated ageing test. From the study, CITA-1 was found to be the best in terms of all the seed quality parameters measured after accelerated ageing with an estimated average storage life of six months (6.31)months and closely followed by CITA-2 with four months (4.56)months while ICPL 87 and AO/TB/78-9 jointly recorded the least values. As ageing duration progresses, CITA-1 consistently recorded the highest germination value. Kuai *et al.*, 2016 and Kehinde *et al.*, 2019 worked on rapeseeds and pigeon pea deterioration respectively, and predicted seed viability in storage under constant conditions for different species under different storage environments. From

the study, CITA-1 had the highest time taken for seed lot to lose 1 probit viability as it takes approximately one hundred and fifteen (115) days to attain 50% viability in storage, and it also had an estimated storage life of 6.31 months.

Conclusion

These findings have further established that ageing time significantly affected the physiological quality of eight genotypes of pigeon pea. The quality of evaluated seeds deteriorated with increase in ageing period. CITA-1 had the highest mean value in all the physiological parameters evaluated and also had the highest estimated seed storage life (6.31 months). CITA-1 and AO/TB-78-9 are therefore recommended for future seed improvement due to their high display of vigour and storability potential under accelerated ageing.

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